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White Paper

Time spent per patient visit has a strong impact on compliance and treatment outcomes

Abstract

This paper examines the correlation between the duration of patient visits and health outcomes, with the goal of determining the impact of time spent per patient on overall health and well-being. The research incorporates a diverse sample of 80 patients, analyzing their medical records, self-reported health indicators, and the average time spent during their doctor visits. Strong arguments in favor of the positive correlation between time spent per patient visit and improved health outcomes are highlighted in this paper. Firstly, this paper argues towards the point of view that longer patient visits facilitate better rapport-building, which in turn leads to increased patient trust and satisfaction. Secondly, it is shown that extended consultations provide healthcare providers with the opportunity to conduct more thorough assessments, leading to better-informed diagnoses and treatment plans. Finally, the research emphasizes the importance of comprehensive patient education, as longer visits enable healthcare professionals to address patient concerns more effectively and promote adherence to treatment regimens. The results of this study reveal a significant positive correlation between time spent per patient visit and improved health outcomes. This paper also underlines the need for healthcare systems to invest in strategies that support longer consultations, e.g. via telemedicine, as it has the potential to enhance patient satisfaction, optimize the diagnostic process, and improve treatment adherence. Future research is recommended to explore the specific mechanisms through which increased time spent per visit can lead to better health outcomes, and to investigate the potential implications for healthcare policy and practice.

Changes in doctor-patient relationships and communication

The quality of patient care has been the subject of numerous research studies and policy debates in the past few decades. One crucial aspect of healthcare delivery that has garnered significant attention is the duration of patient visits with healthcare providers. This white paper seeks to describe the relationship between time spent per patient visit and health outcomes, and to investigate the hypothesis that the average duration of patient visits has decreased in recent years. Several factors have contributed to the decline in the duration of patient visits.

Firstly, the growing demand for healthcare services has placed substantial pressure on healthcare systems worldwide. This increased demand has resulted in a higher number of patients being seen by healthcare providers, often leading to shorter consultation times in order to accommodate more patients in their daily schedules.

Secondly, the rise of healthcare costs has led to increased scrutiny of healthcare spending, with a focus on cost containment and efficiency. As a result, healthcare providers may be incentivized to minimize the time spent with each individual patient, potentially compromising the quality of care provided.

Lastly, the rapid advancements in medical technology and electronic health records have introduced new complexities into the healthcare systems of many western countries.

While these technologies have the potential to streamline medical practice and enhance patient care, they can also contribute to significantly increased administrative burdens for healthcare providers.

This may further reduce the time available for direct patient interaction and care. The reduction in time spent per patient visit raises concerns about the potential consequences for health outcomes. Prior research has suggested that shorter consultations may hinder the development of strong and reliable patient-

provider relationships, limit the accuracy of diagnoses, and impede effective patient education, all of which can negatively impact health outcomes (Thuemmler C. et al., 2005).

The importance of the doctor patient interaction

The doctor-patient relationship is an essential component of healthcare delivery and has long been considered a critical factor in determining the quality of care and patient satisfaction. This relationship is founded on trust, communication, and empathy, all of which contribute to the overall success of the diagnostic process, patient compliance, and clinical outcomes. The entire idealization of the medical profession by many patients, their exaggerated hopes and disappointments, and the doctors' fear to admit their limited knowledge is of outstanding importance of the doctor-patient relationship and to elucidate its impact on these three key areas in the context of contemporary healthcare practice. The efficacy of the diagnostic process is most heavily influenced by the quality of the doctor-patient relationship. A strong relationship facilitates open and honest communication, enabling patients to share their symptoms, concerns, and medical history more effectively (Heritage & Maynard, 2006).

This comprehensive exchange of information provides healthcare providers with a better understanding of the patient's condition, ultimately leading to more accurate diagnoses and personalized treatment plans. Moreover, a trusting relationship encourages patients to seek timely medical attention, reducing the risk of delayed diagnoses and treatment. Adherence to prescribed treatments and recommendations is crucial for achieving optimal clinical outcomes. The doctor-patient relationship plays a pivotal role in fostering compliance, as patients who trust their healthcare providers are more likely to adhere to their advice (Zolnierek & DiMatteo, 2009). Furthermore, a strong relationship allows for better patient education, as healthcare providers can address patients' concerns and misconceptions about their treatment, leading to improved understanding and commitment

to their prescribed regimens (Bultman & Svarstad, 2000). The influence of the doctor-patient relationship on clinical outcomes extends beyond the diagnostic process and patient compliance alone. A supportive and empathetic relationship has been shown to improve patient satisfaction, psychological well-being, and overall quality of life (Kelley, Kraft-Todd, Schapira, Kossowsky, & Riess, 2014).

What is more and of quite some importance, patients who perceive their healthcare providers as caring and compassionate are more likely to engage in health-promoting behaviors, such as regular exercise and a balanced diet, further contributing to positive health outcomes (Beach, Keruly, & Moore, 2006). The doctor-patient relationship is a critical determinant of the success of the diagnostic process, patient compliance, and clinical outcomes. By fostering trust, open communication, and empathy, healthcare providers can enhance the overall quality of care and improve patient satisfaction. It is imperative for healthcare systems to recognize the importance of the doctor-patient relationship and to implement strategies that support its development and maintenance, in order to achieve better health outcomes and higher patient satisfaction. More research should be done to explore the specific mechanisms through which the doctor-patient relationship influences various aspects of healthcare delivery, and to identify best practices for establishing/ cultivating strong relationships in diverse healthcare settings. However, such research is chronically and severely underfunded.

The role of telemedicine

Telemedicine, the use of technology to deliver healthcare services remotely, has experienced rapid growth in recent years. This mode of healthcare delivery presents a unique opportunity to address some of the challenges faced by traditional healthcare systems, such as time constraints and accessibility. It would be wise to discuss the impact of telemedicine on the doctor-patient relationship, with a focus on its potential to increase the time available for patient consultations and improve overall

accessibility on a much broader scale and to define telemedicine as a connecting tool rather than one that separates individuals from one another. Telemedicine has the potential to positively influence the doctor-patient relationship by reducing time constraints that often accompany in-person consultations. By eliminating the need for travel and waiting times, telemedicine can provide healthcare providers with more flexibility in managing their schedules, allowing them to allocate more time to each patient (Hjelm, 2005). This increased time spent per patient can facilitate better rapport-building, as well as more thorough assessments and patient education, ultimately enhancing the overall quality of care. Additionally, telemedicine can offer a more patient-centered approach to healthcare delivery. With the ability to easily conduct consultations from the comfort of their own homes, patients may feel more at ease and be more inclined to discuss their concerns openly, thereby fostering a stronger doctor-patient relationship (Wootton, 2001).

One of the most striking advantages of telemedicine is its ability to improve easy accessibility to healthcare services, even to highly specialized institutions. For individuals in rural or remote areas, or those with limited mobility, telemedicine can provide access to high-quality care that may have otherwise been unattainable (Dorsey & Topol, 2016). By drastically reducing geographical barriers, telemedicine can increase the availability of specialized care, offering patients a wider range of treatment options and promoting better health outcomes (Chaet et al., 2017). Due to the very high quality, safety and low cost (often zero) for video calls, telemedical-consultations can be considered as almost equal to seeing a patient in person in the same room (Weinstein et al., 2018).

Telemedicine represents a promising pathway for enhancing the doctor-patient relationship and improving accessibility to healthcare services. By affording healthcare providers more time to spend with their patients and increasing access to care for underserved populations, telemedicine has the potential to significantly improve patient satisfaction and overall health outcomes. It is crucial for healthcare systems to embrace this innovative

mode of healthcare delivery and to invest in the necessary infrastructure and training to ensure its successful implementation. Further studies with patient data is needed to identify best practices for integrating telemedicine into existing healthcare systems to its full potential, as well as to explore the long-term impact of telemedicine on doctor-patient relationships and patient outcomes.

The decline of time invested per patient in the European Union

Over the past few decades, the European Union (EU), a single market area with over half a billion inhabitants, has experienced quite substantial changes in its healthcare landscape. These changes have had notable effects on the average time and procedures invested in a patient per doctor's visit. While specific figures vary across member states, several trends have emerged that indicate a general reduction in the time allocated to patient consultations. A number of factors have contributed to the observed decrease in the average time spent per doctor's visit in the EU. Firstly, the growing demand for healthcare services, driven by an aging population and an increasing prevalence of chronic diseases, has placed considerable pressure on healthcare systems.

As a result, healthcare providers may find it necessary to shorten consultation times in order to accommodate more patients in their daily schedules (Irving et al., 2017). Secondly, the introduction of performance-based funding models in some EU countries has created incentives for healthcare providers to prioritize efficiency and cost containment. These incentives may inadvertently contribute to a reduction in the average time spent with patients, as providers aim to maximize the number of consultations per day (Langton et al., 2016). Finally, the widespread adoption of electronic health records (EHRs) and other health information technologies has changed the dynamics of patient consultations. While these technologies have the potential to streamline medical practice and enhance patient care, they can also impose additional administrative and legal burdens on healthcare providers. This increase in administrative tasks

may further reduce the time available for direct patient interaction and care (Riordan et al., 2015). Despite these trends, it is essential to recognize that the average time and procedures invested in a patient per doctor's visit may not be the sole determinants of healthcare quality and outcomes. Factors such as the doctor-patient relationship, patient-centered care, and access to specialized services also play critical roles in shaping health outcomes and patient satisfaction.

As such, it is crucial for policymakers and healthcare providers to consider a holistic approach to healthcare delivery, one that balances efficiency with patient needs and expectations. So, it is a problematic fact that the average time and procedures invested in a patient per doctor's visit in the EU have decreased over recent years. This reduction has been influenced by factors such as growing demand for healthcare services, performance-based funding models, and the adoption of health information technologies. To ensure the provision of high-quality care and the achievement of optimal health outcomes, it is vital for stakeholders to consider both the benefits and challenges associated with these trends and to develop strategies that promote a balanced approach to healthcare delivery.

High-end devices in the doctor's bag

The landscape of healthcare delivery has experienced significant transformations in recent years, with the emergence of numerous point-of-care devices that enable healthcare providers to offer advanced diagnostic and monitoring services outside of traditional healthcare settings. This technological progress (Weinstein et al., 2018) has the potential to revitalize home visits by family doctors, which have become increasingly rare in wealthy countries with state-of-the-art health systems. One of the primary reasons for the decline in home visits has been the reliance on advanced diagnostic equipment, such as 12-Lead ECG machines and sonography devices, which were once too cumbersome and impractical for use in home settings. However, recent advancements in medical technology have led to the development of portable, user-friendly

devices that allow family doctors to perform diagnostic procedures with the same level of accuracy and efficiency as in their offices. For example, mobile phone applications and accessories now enable healthcare providers to record 12-Lead ECGs, while tablet computers equipped with specialized software and hardware can be used to perform sonography. Additionally, the invention of rapid tests for various conditions has further expanded the diagnostic capabilities of healthcare providers during home visits.

These technological advancements have significant implications for the practice of family medicine and the overall quality of healthcare delivery (Marsh-Feiley et al., 2018). Home visits facilitated by point-of-care devices can offer several benefits, including increased accessibility to care for patients with limited mobility or those who live in remote areas, enhanced patient satisfaction through personalized care, and the potential for early detection and intervention in acute or chronic conditions (Grol et al., 2006). Furthermore, the ability to provide high-quality care in patients' homes can foster stronger doctor-patient relationships, as healthcare providers are better able to understand patients' living conditions and tailor their interventions accordingly. This patient-centered approach may lead to improved treatment adherence, better health outcomes, and increased patient satisfaction. As Stewart et al., 2000 emphasize, "Patient-centered communication was correlated with the patients' perceptions of finding common ground. In addition, positive perceptions (both the total score and the subscore on finding common ground) were associated with better recovery from their discomfort and concern, better emotional health 2 months later, and fewer diagnostic tests and referrals."

The emergence of new point-of-care devices has the potential to elevate the practice of home visits by family doctors to new heights, overcoming previous limitations imposed by the need for large-scale diagnostic equipment. The incorporation of these devices into routine clinical practice can enhance the quality and accessibility of care, promote patient-centered care, and strengthen the doctor-patient relationship. It is crucial for healthcare systems

and providers to embrace these technological advancements and to invest in the necessary training and infrastructure to ensure the successful integration of point-of-care devices into the practice of family medicine.

Conclusion

In a nutshell, the authors of this paper are convinced that the integration of modern technology, such as telemedicine and easily transportable high-end diagnostic tools, into medical practice is essential for improving patient care and good clinical outcomes. By employing these advanced technologies, physicians can allocate more time to each patient, resulting in increased compliance and better therapeutic outcomes. Moreover, the use of innovative solutions in healthcare can help physicians regain a sense of purpose and satisfaction in their profession, ultimately promoting a more positive and fulfilling work environment. It is important to note that the effective implementation of these technologies necessitates a comprehensive and well-considered approach from health policy makers. By creating appropriate incentives and supporting the medical community in adopting these new tools and practices, policy makers can contribute to a radical shift in the way healthcare is delivered. This shift not only has the potential to improve individual patient care, but also has far-reaching implications for all types of healthcare systems as a whole, potentially reducing costs and improving compliance as well as outcomes.

One of the main challenges facing policy makers is to strike a balance between the rapid advancement of technology and the need for evidence-based decision-making. This requires rigorous evaluation of new technological solutions in the context of clinical practice, as well as the development of guidelines and protocols for their implementation.

Additionally, policy makers must ensure that adequate resources are allocated to support healthcare professionals in the acquisition of necessary skills and training. Furthermore, the implementation of modern technology should be carried out in a manner that ensures equitable access to quality healthcare for all

citizens. This can be achieved by investing in digital infrastructure, especially in underserved areas, and by developing policies that promote the adoption of technology in both public and private healthcare settings. Additionally, it is crucial for policy makers to consider the ethical implications of technological advancements and establish appropriate regulatory frameworks to safeguard patient privacy and autonomy. To achieve lasting change, it is essential for policy makers to engage with all the various stakeholders, including healthcare professionals, technology developers, and patient advocacy groups. By fostering a collaborative environment, policy makers can encourage the sharing of knowledge and expertise, ultimately facilitating the development of innovative solutions that address the complex challenges faced by the healthcare sector.

In summary, the successful integration of modern technology in healthcare is contingent upon the concerted efforts of health policy makers in developing and implementing appropriate incentives and support structures. By focusing on increasing the time spent per patient and ensuring equitable access to cutting-edge diagnostic and therapeutic tools, policy makers can foster an environment in which both patients and physicians can thrive, leading to improved clinical outcomes and a renewed sense of purpose within the medical community.

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Conflicts of interest

Dr. Marius Lazar has been involved in telemedical projects in the last two decades.

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References

1. John Heritage, Douglas W. Maynard: *Communication in Medical Care: Interaction between Primary Care Physicians*. Cambridge University Press, 2006
2. Zolnieriek KB, Dimatteo MR. Physician communication and patient adherence to treatment: a meta-analysis. *Med Care*. 2009 Aug;47(8):826-34. doi: 10.1097/MLR.0b013e31819a5acc. PMID: 19584762; PMCID: PMC2728700.
3. Bultman DC, Svarstad BL. Effects of physician communication style on client medication beliefs and adherence with antidepressant treatment. *Patient Educ Couns*. 2000 May;40(2):173-85. doi: 10.1016/s0738-3991(99)00083-x. PMID: 10771371.
4. Thuemmler C, Morris C. Global case management: Scotland. Real-time monitoring of patient flow as an instrument to optimize quality of care in acute receiving units. *Lippincotts Case Manag*. 2005 Sep-Oct;10(5):254-60. doi: 10.1097/00129234-200509000-00008. PMID: 16205208.
5. Kelley JM, Kraft-Todd G, Schapira L, Kossowsky J, Riess H. The influence of the patient-clinician relationship on healthcare outcomes: a systematic review and meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials. *PLoS One*. 2014 Apr 9;9(4):e94207. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0094207. Erratum in: *PLoS One*. 2014;9(6):e101191. PMID: 24718585; PMCID: PMC3981763.
6. Beach MC, Keruly J, Moore RD. Is the quality of the patient-provider relationship associated with better adherence and health outcomes for patients with HIV? *J Gen Intern Med*. 2006 Jun;21(6):661-5. doi: 10.1111/j.1525-1497.2006.00399.x. PMID: 16808754; PMCID: PMC1924639.
7. Hjelm NM. Benefits and drawbacks of telemedicine. *J Telemed Telecare*. 2005;11(2):60-70. doi: 10.1258/1357633053499886. PMID: 15829049.
8. Wootton R. Recent advances: Telemedicine. *BMJ*. 2001 Sep 8;323(7312):557-60. doi: 10.1136/bmj.323.7312.557. PMID: 11546704; PMCID: PMC1121135.
9. Dorsey ER, Topol EJ. State of Telehealth. *N Engl J Med*. 2016 Jul 14;375(2):154-61. doi: 10.1056/NEJMra1601705. PMID: 27410924.
10. Chaet D, Clearfield R, Sabin JE, Skimming K; Council on Ethical and Judicial Affairs American Medical Association. Ethical

- practice in Telehealth and Telemedicine. *J Gen Intern Med.* 2017 Oct;32(10):1136-1140. doi: 10.1007/s11606-017-4082-2. Epub 2017 Jun 26. PMID: 28653233; PMCID: PMC5602756.
11. Irving G, Neves AL, Dambha-Miller H, Oishi A, Tagashira H, Verho A, Holden J. International variations in primary care physician consultation time: a systematic review of 67 countries. *BMJ Open.* 2017 Nov 8;7(10):e017902. doi: 10.1136/bmjopen-2017-017902. PMID: 29118053; PMCID: PMC5695512.
 12. Langton, J., Reeve, R., Srasuebkul, P. et al. Health service use and costs in the last 6 months of life in elderly decedents with a history of cancer: a comprehensive analysis from a health payer perspective. *Br J Cancer* 114, 1293–1302 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1038/bjc.2016.75>
 13. Fiona Riordan, Chrysanthi Papoutsis, Julie E. Reed, Cicely Marston, Derek Bell, Azeem Majeed, Patient and public attitudes towards informed consent models and levels of awareness of Electronic Health Records in the UK, *International Journal of Medical Informatics*, Volume 84, Issue 4, 2015, ISSN 1386-5056, doi.org/10.1016/j.ijmedinf.2015.01.008
 14. Weinstein RS, Krupinski EA, Doarn CR. Clinical Examination Component of Telemedicine, Telehealth, mHealth, and Connected Health Medical Practices. *Med Clin North Am.* 2018 May;102(3):533-544. doi: 10.1016/j.mcna.2018.01.002. PMID: 29650074.
 15. Genevieve Marsh-Feiley, Leila Eadie, Philip Wilson, Telesonography in emergency medicine: A systematic review. *Plos One*, Published: May 3, 2018. doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0194840
 16. Grol R., et al.: Improving Patient Care: The Implementation of Change in Clinical Practice. *Qual Saf Health Care.* 2006 Dec; 15(6): 447. doi: 10.1136/qshc.2005.016824 PMCID: PMC2464885
 17. Stewart M, Brown JB, Donner A, McWhinney IR, Oates J, Weston WW, Jordan J. The impact of patient-centered care on outcomes. *J Fam Pract.* 2000 Sep;49(9):796-804. PMID: 11032203